

Supplementary Materials: Behavioral strategies of prehistoric and historic children from dental microwear texture analysis

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Table S1: List of specimens studied

Specimen	Cultural context	Tooth	Reference
El Castillo 924	Mousterian	ULdi1	Garralda et al., 2022
El Sidrón SD1721	Mousterian	URdc	Rosas et al., 2013; Rosas et al., 2017
Engis 2	Mousterian	ULdi1	Tillier, 1983
Krapina_13	Mousterian	LLdi2	Radovčić et al., 1988
LaChaise_S14-2	Mousterian	LRdi1	Piveteau, 1982; Teihol, 2001
LaChaise_S14-3	Mousterian	LRdi2	Piveteau, 1982; Teihol, 2001
LaChaiseBD_BD19	Mousterian	LRdc	Condemi, 2001; Teihol, 2001
PechdelAze_1	Mousterian	URdi1	Soressi et al., 2007
Qafzeh_10	Mousterian UP	ULdc	Tillier, 1980
Qafzeh_4	Mousterian UP	URdc	Tillier, 1980
Pavlov_13	Gravettian	di	Sládek et al., 2000; Hillson, 2006; Svoboda, 2006
Pavlov_14	Gravettian	dc	Sládek et al., 2000; Hillson, 2006; Svoboda, 2006
Pavlov_16	Gravettian	di	Sládek et al., 2000; Hillson, 2006; Svoboda, 2006
Pavlov_18	Gravettian	di	Sládek et al., 2000; Hillson, 2006; Svoboda, 2006

Solutre	Solutrean	LRdi2	Tompkins, 1996
SaintGermain_1970-7-4	Magdalenian	di	Gambier et al., 2000
SaintGermain_1970-7-8	Magdalenian	dc	Gambier et al., 2000
StGermain_B3	Magdalenian	LLdc	Blanchard et al., 1972
Mazo #200	Chalcolithic	Ulde	González Rabanal, 2022
Espinoso Nicho 3 #43	Bronze Age	LRdi2	González Rabanal, 2022
Abrigo de la Castañera#133	Bronze Age	ULdc	González Rabanal, 2022
Abrigo de la Castañera #198	Bronze Age	URdc	González Rabanal, 2022
Amarna_Egypt_SK11	Historic-Amarna	Ldc	Kemp, 2005; Rose, 2006
Amarna_Egypt_SK195	Historic-Amarna	Rdi1	Kemp, 2005; Rose, 2006
Amarna_Egypt_SK198	Historic-Amarna	Ldi1	Kemp, 2005; Rose, 2006
Amarna_Egypt_SK199	Historic-Amarna	Ldc	Kemp, 2005; Rose, 2006
Amarna_Egypt_SK242	Historic-Amarna	Rdi2	Kemp, 2005; Rose, 2006
Amarna_Egypt_SK243	Historic-Amarna	Rdi1	Kemp, 2005; Rose, 2006
Amarna_Egypt_SK244	Historic-Amarna	Ldi1	Kemp, 2005; Rose, 2006
Amarna_Egypt_SK258	Historic-Amarna	Rdi1	Kemp, 2005; Rose, 2006
Amarna_Egypt_SK272	Historic-Amarna	Rdc	Kemp, 2005; Rose, 2006
Amarna_Egypt_SK274	Historic-Amarna	Rdc	Kemp, 2005; Rose, 2006
Amarna_Egypt_SK312	Historic-Amarna	Rdi1	Kemp, 2005; Rose, 2006

Amarna_Egypt_SK330	Historic-Amarna	Rdi2	Kemp, 2005; Rose, 2006
Amarna_Egypt_I192	Historic-Amarna	Ldc	Kemp, 2005; Rose, 2006
Amarna_Egypt_I373	Historic-Amarna	Ldc	Kemp, 2005; Rose, 2006
Amarna_Egypt_SK304	Historic-Amarna	Ldi1	Kemp, 2005; Rose, 2006
Amarna_Egypt_SK284	Historic-Amarna	Rdi1	Kemp, 2005; Rose, 2006
Amarna_Egypt_SK197	Historic-Amarna	Rdi1	Kemp, 2005; Rose, 2006
Amarna_Egypt_SK196	Historic-Amarna	Rdi1	Kemp, 2005; Rose, 2006
Amarna_Egypt_SK238	Historic-Amarna	Ldi1	Kemp, 2005; Rose, 2006
Ipiutak_PointHope_83	Historic-Point Hope	URdi1	Krueger, 2006; Dabbs, 2009
Ipiutak_PointHope_108	Historic-Point Hope	ULdi1	Krueger, 2006; Dabbs, 2009
Ipiutak_PointHope_167	Historic-Point Hope	URdi1	Krueger, 2006; Dabbs, 2009
Tigara_PointHope_244	Historic-Point Hope	URdi1	Krueger, 2006; Dabbs, 2009
Tigara_PointHope_273	Historic-Point Hope	URdi1	Krueger, 2006; Dabbs, 2009
Tigara_PointHope_280	Historic-Point Hope	ULdi1	Krueger, 2006; Dabbs, 2009

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